

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MICALLEF****FIRST NAME: CRISTINA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which are the main steps required to achieve a ‘logical flow/ in dissertations/long papers?’**
 - Commence by drafting the paper/dissertation and then insert headings, subheadings accordingly.
 - Commence by inserting headings and then start drafting, linking paragraphs and section with words such as ‘however’, ‘on the other hand’.¹**
 - Commence by inserting headings while you are drafting paper/dissertation.
 - Commence by inserting headings and then start drafting, and not link paragraphs and section with words such as ‘however’, ‘on the other hand’.

1. Euclid University *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2015), 40.

2. **Why is it NOT acceptable to not include the source of information in a document?**

- Plagiarism is unethical, wrong, and a serious offence in academic writing.²**
- Citing gives credibility to your research project.
- Plagiarism does not make other people's work your own.
- Plagiarism does not discredit your research project.

3. **Why is it important to use a standardized in-house style guide, such as the WHO Style Guide?**

- Standardization makes it more difficult for researchers, and readers to find the information that they are looking for.
- It offers unnecessary stress resulting in decreased efficiency within the institution.
- It offers consistency, an image of unity within the institution, streamlines and increases efficiency during the writing, and editing process.³**
- Style uniformity leads to inconsistent terminology, punctuation, formatting, etc.

2. EUCLID, 12.

3. World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004),1.

4. **What are the main objectives of literature review?**

- Literature review is another chapter within your dissertation to make it longer.
- To find arguments in favour and against your hypothesis, and to retrieve as much evidence as possible.**⁴
- Literature review is important to support your hypothesis.
- Literature review is important to establish a chronological history of findings.

5. **Which important features a figure in a dissertation/paper must have?**

- Figures should have a title and axes labelled and numbered separately from tables.
- Figures should have a title and data points clearly explained and data presented clearly.
- Figures should not have the data clearly presented, have a title axes labelled, data points clearly explained and numbered separately from tables.
- Figures should have the data clearly presented, have a title, axes labelled, data points clearly explained and numbered separately from tables.**⁵

4. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 31.

5. Kate L. Turabian, 219-20.

6. **Which elements do the Turabian style include in in-text citations?**

- Author's last name, author's first name, year of publication.
- Author's last name, author's first name, year of publication, page, title of book, place of publication.
- Author, year of publication, page and place of publication.
- Author, date of publication and relevant page number.⁶**

7. **Methodology is the basis of the research project, which important elements should NOT be undiscussed in this chapter?**

- The strengths and weaknesses of the study, the sampling methodology, safeguard of confidentiality and anonymity, method used for data collection and the reason for choosing these methods, and any biases.⁷**
- The methodology used for data collection and sampling only.
- Confidentiality and anonymity should not be discussed.
- Biases should not be discussed as this will lead to a decrease in credibility of the study presented.

6. Kate L. Turabian, 128.

7. Kate L. Turabian, 69-78.

8. **An important part of research is the presentation of data and its analysis, which are the most common variables, in a qualitative study calculated?**
- Range, percentage, and average.
 - Percentage, incidence, and prevalence.
 - Mean, median, and mode.⁸**
 - Incidence, prevalence, and mortality rates.
9. **How is qualitative substantive significance identified. It is identified by asking the following question(s)...**
- How do the findings assist new policies, services, and new research, irrespective whether they are robust or not?
 - How do the findings contribute to new knowledge and policies?
 - How do the findings offer better understanding of the research being presented?
 - How do the findings assist in understanding further the research topic and by what extent, how robust are they, what level of support do they offer to current knowledge, whether they offer new findings, and do they offer information regarding the development of policies, services, or new theories?⁹**

8. Linda D. Bloomberg, and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 97.

9. Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 130-31.

10. **Conclusions and recommendations are NOT the least important in a dissertation. Why?**

- Conclusions and recommendations lead to more research.
- Conclusions and recommendations are the most important because they lead to less research and more policies.
- They are the conclusion of each finding, from which recommendations can be developed and can be implemented in the area being researched, leading to long-term benefits.**
- Conclusions and recommendations are two separate outcomes of the findings and lead to further research with less long-term benefits.¹⁰

10. Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 157-58.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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